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The Survey of India in WWII

Mapping Archaeological Heritage in South Asia

May 9, 2023

The Survey of India's role in the World Wars

The Survey of India was a department under the control of the Government of India (although it was not a government department), and was never under direct control of the War Department itself. Even so, the Survey of India played an indispensable role in military operations.

Indian and Anglo-Indian surveyors often had a lack of recognition in comparison to their white British counterparts, being paid less, and their names are rarely mentioned in documents and post-war scholarship. The story below is a rare example of the recognition of the work of some of the Indian surveyors such as M.Z.A. Quraishi, D.C. Kuthari, Zarif Khan, and Sepoy Qurban Ali.

Through surveying the vast and varied terrains of the Indian subcontinent, the staff of the Survey of India became some of the best trained and well regarded surveyors in the world,

and were well known for their ability to work in extremely difficult conditions. Due to this their surveying skills were directed to other colonial territories in the Middle East and Africa where much of the previous mapping of the region was inaccurate. The need for accurate maps of any territory where troops might be deployed at any given time cannot be understated. In WWI, the consequences of cartographic inaccuracies were felt during military campaigns, where overconfidence in poor mapping, and a lack of trust in Ottoman cartography, often misled military leadership, resulting in dire consequences for troops on the ground (Foliard, 2017). Accurate and up to date mapping of the eastern fronts became a priority.

In early 1940, at the outbreak of WWII, Britain grew concerned about German access to the Persian Gulf and oil fields. In August 1941 the neutral Imperial State of Iran was invaded by the United Kingdom and the Soviet Union in the **Anglo-Soviet invasion of Persia**.

The invasion's strategic purpose was to ensure the safety of Allied supply lines to the USSR (known as the Persian Corridor), to secure Iranian oil fields, limit German influence, and pre-empt any possible Axis advancement from Turkey through Iran to British India.

The survey material gathered in Mesopotamia and in East and West Persia during WWI proved to be of crucial strategic importance to the British in WWII during the occupation of Iran and Iraq. Maps continued to be published but certain maps, especially those listing buildings of military importance (army barracks, forts etc.) and details of military operations were set aside and 'For Official Use Only' or 'Secret'.

5. No maps of any part of India whether prepared by the Survey or otherwise may be sent out of India without sanction by Army Headquarters.
6. Maps of neutral countries may be sent out of India provided that : -
- they are maps which are on sale to the public.
 - they are for export only to the contry they represent.
7. Plans or photographs reproducing topographical features on maps of India may not be sent out of India without reference to Army Headquarters.

1940 correspondence dictating that Indian maps should be classified as 'secret'

Example of a map from the NW of India (now Pakistan) made 'secret' during WWII

Linking Iraq and India: Trans-Persia Triangulation 1941-1944

In 1941 British and Indian Forces (the 10th Army, later Paiforce) moved into Iraq and Persia and a Survey Directorate was formed at Baghdad. This comprised four Indian Field Survey Companies under a DD Survey who received instructions from Director of Survey, India.

Initially, attention was given to revising the existing maps as far as possible along communication lines. It was later deemed necessary to carry out a considerable amount of triangulation in northwest Persia, and a flurry of new

mapping began. Between 1941 and 1943 some 70,000 square miles of country was covered by triangulation to connect Persia to India, as seen in the map below.

Nain-Zahidan Triangulation (Persia - India Connection) completed by the Survey of India team

List of personnel

Capt. P. A. Thomas, I.R.			
Capt. F. J. Satur, I.A.M.C.			
Subedar M. Z. A. Quraishi.			
Jemadar Svyr. Mauji Ram.			
.. .. A. S. Rana.			
.. .. H. U. Khan.			
.. .. Autar Singh.			
.. Clerk M. G. Rasul.			
Havildar Computer D. C. Kuthari.			
I.O.Rs. Survey	..	..	30
Drivers M.T.	..	..	21
Signallers	..	..	8
Fitters	..	..	3
Electrician	..	..	1
Carpenter	..	..	1
Nursing orderly	..	..	1
Interpreter	..	..	1

List of personnel working on the Nain-Zahidan Triangulation, including South Asian surveyors

Here, we join the journey with the determined Survey of India team in 1944 as they traverse their way from Baghdad to the border of northwest India (modern Pakistan).

Earthstar Geographics

500 km Powered by Esri

1 From Baghdad, Iraq

A convoy of 18 vehicles and 75 people left Baghdad on the morning of December 29th 1943

2 Khanaqin, Iraq

10 miles from Khanaqin the convoy was mistakenly led to the wrong staging camp by 2 red cap dispatch riders. At the camp, no one knew who the surveyors were or what to do with them, and they were forced to move about 4 miles further to camp.

3 Arak, Iran

Arak was reached on New Year's Day. Here, the team stayed for a day to purchase extra rations and collect items for the cold winter ahead, as well as carry out some repairs to the vehicles.

4 Isfahan, Iran

The convoy reached Isfahan and camp was pitched about 15 miles from the town. So far the surveyors had suffered through extremely poor weather with cold, intense winds and clouds. The surveyors debated beginning the triangulation from here, but with such limited time for this enormous project, it was decided they would continue to Nain before beginning their triangulations.

5 Nain, Iran

The convoy reached Nain on the 8th of January. The vision was so good that a distance estimated to be 14 miles was in fact 36! This meant that the following work could be broken up into larger chunks.

First, the 40-mile broad valley, 500 miles long, flanked by snow covered mountain ranges rising from 7000 ft at Nain to 15000 ft at Kerman, with the short sharp descent to desert level of 2000 ft at Bam; secondly, the 100-mile stretch of flat Lut Desert, and finally the 100 miles of massed mountains, averaging 8000 ft, to the west of Zahidan.

6

On the 14th of January the party departed Nain with the plan for more observations on the 15th. It quickly became apparent, however, that their elaborate plan was doomed to fail as it was not possible to cater for the innumerable obstacles they would be met with.

By the 20th of January they had suffered through mechanical breakdowns, bogged down vehicles, the inability to climb hills due to physical difficulties such as snow, ice and rain, variable weather throughout the days including cyclonic icy winds, and dust haze. The difficulty of maintaining each survey party with enough water, petrol, kerosene, rations and clothing meant that a breakdown anywhere led to a complete stop to work.

The heliographs (solar telegraph system) used by the parties for the triangulation were extremely weather dependent, which was becoming an issue. All parties reconvened at Nain.

7

Back to Nain

One benefit of the experience of the last few days was the proof that, in good weather, visibility up to 35 miles was always extremely good. Accordingly Subedar Quraishi was taken off observing, and with 2 surveyors and their squads of 4 men and 2 vehicles each, formed an advance recce and cairn building party.

These new observations began January 23rd and in 5 days 5 stations had been completed. Two of these stations were at over 9000 ft and required skilful mountaineering abilities!

To complete one of these observations meant an intense day. Climbing 5000 ft from a camp near the foot in around 4 hours, then taking observations at the top which took another 3 or 4 hours, and finally the descent back to camp in darkness which may take another 3 hours. This was not helped by the short

winter days, which meant leaving camp in the dark and returning after nightfall. Things did not always go as planned...

8

On Station No. 8 the observing party was stuck after a long, perilous descent in darkness. At 1am they reached a caravanserai and begged for food and warmth.

9

At Station No. 9, two members of the party were stuck on the mountainside and spent the night at about 9000 ft without any food or shelter with temperatures well below freezing.

10

At Station No. 12 the wrong peak was climbed and in consequence four days were lost waiting for the haze to clear.

11

Two lives were nearly lost during the ascent of Station 16 when loose shale and slate, made movement extremely dangerous.

12

A night was spent at Station 18 at 13,900 ft with no food, warmth or shelter. Two cases of snow blindness had to be dealt with the next day.

13

Station 19 proved too much for all but three men who had to complete all the work themselves, arriving back to camp at 3am!

14

Bahramabad, Iran

A base was then measured at Bahramabad, connecting the earlier series together in triangular placements.

15

Kerman, Iran

Kerman was reached on March 4th where rations from India were welcomed by the group. For the past few days the men had been living off of dried dates and biscuits.

The greater part of the series was now completed, but it was feared that weather conditions would make the upcoming 100 miles across the Lut Desert more difficult...

16

The Lut Desert

The reconnaissance of the desert portion of the mission proved heartbreaking. The weather was dense with haze, restricting visibility to just 10 miles, and there were no suitable locations to triangulate. For four days the teams wandered fruitlessly around the desert attempting to find better positions. By the fourth day, they were ready to give up and abandon the series completely, however when they awoke on the fifth day, a terrific storm burst, clearing the haze and saving the operation!

17**Nasratabad Sipi, Iran**

It was not until the 6th of April that the desert portion was completed and the main camp established at Nasratabad Sipi for the last lap of the series, with 5 stations remaining to observe. Eventually, on the 18th of April, the last station was observed, and this map series was completed.

18 Zahedan, Iran

The whole party assembled at Zahedan, and after four days of repairing vehicles (several of which had to be evacuated by train), the convoy proceeded on its journey to Quetta.

The final point of this journey was still about 1000 miles away and could not be undertaken without significant repairs to their vehicles and resupplying, which took ten days to complete.

19

Quetta, Pakistan

The 11 day journey to reach Quetta began, arriving finally in the town on the 17th of May. From here, all personnel were given well deserved leave, vehicles were returned to Ordnance and disbandment was completed in 2 weeks. The Angle books and charts were handed in to the Director of War Research, and Survey of India in Dehradun where new maps would be produced and distributed.

A Job Well Done

The work of the Survey of India team triangulating the journey from Persia to India was well received by their

superiors. The tight-knit friendships and camaraderie this mission cultivated are clear in the write-up from the mission supervisor, Major P.A. Thomas

37. The magnitude of the task was never under estimated from the start. A very good idea is provided by the interesting comparison with the map of England and Scotland at the same scale, from which it will be seen that the length of the series was exactly the same length as from John O'Groats to the Isle of Wight. The difficulties and obstacles proved much greater than was imagined. It resolved into a battle against time and against every conceivable kind of obstacle that Nature could produce in the way of weather and country. The completion of the series was always a matter of the greatest doubt and anxiety and on two occasions the abandonment was seriously considered. The successful completion is due, in the main, to the excellent co-operation and help of all who formed the party, and in particular, to Subedar M. Z. A. Quraishi who proved a staunch and willing supporter, to Hav. (now Jemadar) D. C. Kuthari an indefatigable and keen computer and recorder, and to L/Nk. Zarif Khan and Sepoy Qurban Ali for their never failing energy and willingness under the most trying and difficult conditions met with.

From Thomas, P.A. 1946. The Persia-India Connection. Publ. the Surveyor General of India.

The Wider Context

The Indian and Anglo-Indian surveyors of the Survey of India, as they were under the British, were an important part of a wider story of advancing and expanding the science and technology of cartography, and the precursor to modern day geospatial sciences. Their maps allowed the Allies to plan campaigns more effectively in the 'Eastern Front' against an advancing Japanese force. However, as well as creating accurate maps with historic detail, they were also a part of expanding the wider colonial narrative and goals. We want to recognise the work of Indian surveyors, not only in the war effort but in the wider history of mapping, and this can be a tricky line to follow. This is especially true when teams were directed out of the regions of South Asia and into colonial territories or regions 'of interest', such as Africa and the Middle East. We wanted to give recognition but to also acknowledge that there was a broader agenda, on the part of colonial powers, at play.

The contributions by these South Asian surveyors to the development of survey techniques and accurate mapping are important. They not only had important technical skills and trained 'hardiness' to the harsh environments, but they also acted as middle-men, engaging with locals, accessing areas

with difficult terrain, and recounting high levels of detail and specific features. This was vital in remote areas where the sight of Europeans and foreigners may have caused alarm in the populace. Or when colonial powers wished to keep their involvement in the region a secret. The extraordinary stories of the Survey of India, and their Indian surveyors, are not simple stories of adventure and triumph, as with any institution that was part of the colonial machine. Regardless, they are still important stories to tell.

Related Projects & Stories

The MAHSA Project

The landscapes of India and Pakistan guard histories that are vulnerable to time and change. Discovering, documenting and disseminating knowledge of archaeological heritage at danger will help to protect it for the future. The MAHSA team and partners are carrying out remote identification of cultural heritage sites that could be at risk today and in the future in the Indus River Basin and surrounding regions. The MAHSA approach combines remote sensing, historic mapping and machine learning-based algorithms to collect, assess, refine, systematise and import archaeological and cultural heritage site data to an open-source online database, making it possible to identify sites that have not previously been documented, highlight sites that are in danger, and monitor the impact of development and agriculture.

To do so, we have been working on georeferencing more than 2000 Survey of India historic maps, which often unintentionally documented historic and archaeological sites.

Check out other work by the MAHSA project, such as our live georeferencing progress map!

Meet MAHSA

The British Film Institute

If you'd like to see video footage of some of the landscapes, landmarks and local people on a similar trip to the one taken by the Survey of India, this time from India to Persia, see the British Film Institute link below. This film was shot by Sir Clarmont Skrine and shows Zahedan, Birjand, Mashhad, Bajgiran, Bujnurd, Damghan and Persepolis, as well as scenes of Quetta.

BFI Video

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